

FROM CHALLENGES TO OPPORTUNITIES: THE NEW NORMAL'S EFFECT ON STUDENT PRODUCTIVITY AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

Everyone wanted to be educated as it is believed to be a key to the realization of ones' dreams. This will give life to many people and can make them get employment. However, when World Health Organization (WHO) declared 2019 Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) as a global health epidemic in the country and Philippine government declared a state of public health emergency, steps were immediately made towards reducing its spread especially from traditional face to face classroom into virtual classroom. It was this movement that constituted the main research gap which this research intends to fill by being the first one to investigate the perceived impact of new normal on education and factors influencing academic performance. In total, one-hundred thirty-five selected students from Laguna participated in this study. The researchers used self-made questionnaire validated by experts and undergone with reliability testing. Specifically, the study aimed at identifying effects of new normal approach in educations, finding out their significant relationship with factors influencing academic performance and determining significant differences when grouped demographically. The study has identified all variables as effects of new normal approach in education having expressively related with factors affecting academic performance of respondents. Also, substantial findings showed that regardless of demographic profile; it cannot affect their perceptions towards what regards new normality. As a result, concentrating on perceived impacts could be an excellent stage or central objectives for developing delivery plan or series of activities that maximize positive outlooks on educational approach under status.

Keywords: *New Approach in education, Academic Performance factors, Student Productivity,*

INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization (WHO) declared the 2019 Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) as a global health pandemic, while President Rodrigo Roa Duterte declared a public health emergency in the Philippines on March 2020, some of which the government immediately implemented measures to contain and prevent further spread of the disease. Factories stopped operation, school was suspended and Filipinos were asked to remain at home. By that time, class suspension happened on March; has several weeks/months remaining before end of last term of academic year 2019-2020 among Philippine Higher Education Institutions or HEIs. Quality assurance guidelines given by The Commission on Higher Education (CHED) mandated higher education institutions (HEIs) to transition into flexible learning.

Given that the information communication technologies (ICTs) are in a constant state of flux, Dziuban et al. (2018) focused on the outcomes, impacts, and future directions of blended learning (BL) in higher education. The results indicated that BL either maintains access or enhances it for most student groups including minorities and non-minorities. Students consistently rated BL highly effective despite little influences from external and demographic factors. Yet regarding its future trajectory they admit to being unsure but their theoretical principles and empirical observations link it with what has been called 'the new normal'. Specifically within the context of Philippine education system in the new normal period. Winthrop (2020) delved into policy implications, strategies and challenges as regards online and distance education in relation to COVID 19 pandemic. Online learning has raised numerous concerns in higher education prompting institutions to adapt policies and programs in response to the crisis. This has led to widespread adoption of online learning platforms by several countries due to community lockdowns particularly affecting schools.

The study addressed various concerns about Philippine schools during this era of new normal calling for proactive handling of challenges. The main question however remains how quality education can be ensured as well as preparedness for future crises. Technological advancement has made online education an option with much flexibility that would attract different populations across globe. Although there are many similarities between online versus traditional forms of instruction these two methods differ significantly based on approach taken towards them.

While many consider flexible learning as an effective and safest pedagogy; and there may be situations when such courses are needed face-to-face. Nonetheless, there have been heated debates in depth researches about online teaching versus classroom or face-to-face mode but this study does not focus on it instead this study is looking at how new approaches in education affect productivity and academic performance with reference to college students.

This study aims at trying to fill some of these gaps that examines perceived impacts of new normal in education and factors affecting academic performance. Through this research completion, universities and colleges will know what things they can possibly do or attempt to guide students' learning process towards productivity. When it comes to students, since this paper shows how they fare as students learning online what ways they use to catch up with the class. Assessing the variables concerning impact of distance learning and productivity level, and academic performance are important bases for planning instructional delivery. The result of this study is a contribution to the academe. According to the researchers' point of view, academic institution can also venture into the same study quest for an excellent education as we adapt to this new normal.

Research Objectives

The study aims to determine the perceived effects of the new normal to students and identify the factors that may influence to their academic performance and productivity level which may lead to suggest a new framework on the conduct of blended learning. It will specifically strive for:

1. To know the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Gender
 - 1.2 Year Level
 - 1.3 Students' Status
 - 1.4 Geographical Location during Distance Learning
 - 1.5 Internet Connection Provider
 - 1.6 Mobile Devices Used
2. To identify the perceived effects of the new normal approach in education to the respondents based on:
 - 2.1. Fostering Relationships
 - 2.2. Engagement
 - 2.3. Timeliness
 - 2.4. Communications
 - 2.5. Technology
 - 2.6. Organization
 - 2.7. Flexibility
3. To determine the factors that influence the productivity level and academic performance of the respondents in conducting new normal approach in education:
 - 3.1 Time
 - 3.2. Learning Environment
 - 3.3. Peer support
 - 3.4. Proper Guidance
 - 3.5. Family Resources
4. To assess if there are significant relationships between the perceived effects of new normal approach and factors that influence the productivity level and academic performance.
5. To distinguish if there are significant differences on respondents' perceived effects of new normal approach when grouped according to their demographic profiles.

METHODOLOGY

In completion of this study, the researchers conducted a descriptive-correlation research design to achieve the purpose of the study. From beginning of analysis, it is necessary to adopt descriptive correlation as a research design in order to handle the research questions at hand. Thus, the study was able to ascertain and delineate perceived effects of new normal approach in education while establishing factors affecting productivity level and academic performance among selected students. Additionally, it explained how variables such as demographic profiles moderate these relationships. Hence, this study used descriptive – correlation because it describes factors that affect productivity level and academic performance of students in addition to establishing relationship between perceived effects of new normal approach. Moreover, identifying significant differences on respondents' perceptions towards the effects of new normal approach according to their demography.

Correlational study uses default numbers for correlational studies in Laguna based on G-Power Statistical Tools. Questionnaire was used by researcher as a major instrument for data gathering purposes needed in this particular study. It was a self-made questionnaire developed by the researcher specifically designed for this survey which help them asses about “the effects of new normal approach”, “productivity” & “academic performance”. In preparing questionnaires they converted each variable information into an item line. Before submitting it from the research expert who check every question precisely.

Table 1. Compositions of Survey Questionnaire

OBJECTIVE	PARTS OF SURVEY	QUESTIONS
1. Know the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:		1.1.1 – 1.1.2
1.1 Gender	Part 1 / Demographic Profile Instrument	1.2.1 – 1.2.3
1.2 Year Level		1.3.1 – 1.3.3
1.3 Students' Status		1.4.1 – 1.4.7
1.4 Geographical Location during Online Classes		1.5.1 – 1.5.5
1.5 Internet Connection Provider		1.6.1 – 1.6.4
1.6 Mobile Devices Used		
2. Identify the perceived effects of the new normal approach in education to the respondents based on:	Part 2 / Perceived Effects Questionnaire	
2.1 Fostering Relationship		2.1.1 – 2.1.9
2.2 Engagement		2.2.1 – 2.2.9
2.3 Timeliness		2.3.1 – 2.3.9
2.4 Communication		2.4.1 – 2.4.9

2.5 Technology		2.5.1 – 2.5.9
2.6 Organization		2.6.1 – 2.6.9
2.7 Flexibility		2.7.1.-2.7.9
3. Determine the factors that influence the productivity level and academic performance of the respondents in conducting new normal approach in education:		
3.1 Time	Part 3 / Questionnaire	Factor 3.1.1 – 3.1.9
3.2 Learning Environment		3.2.1.- 3.2.9
3.3 Peer Support		3.3.1 – 3.3.9
3.4 Proper Guidance		3.4.1 – 3.4.9
3.5 Family Resources		3.5.1 – 3.5.9

The researchers requested validation and approval of questionnaire during proposal defence from panel evaluators. They then revised questionnaire after receiving feedbacks made from panel evaluators. For validation purposes of survey questionnaire, researchers relied on related literature and other studies where they obtained related data. In addition, another expert validation was sought so as to assess if data collection tools were capable enough with high confidence levels to answer objectives of study. One language editor checked it once again for possible mistakes. Lastly, during reliability testing; Cronbach alpha test is based on recommendation by statistician for its recommendations

Table 2. Results of Pilot Testing

RESEARCH VARIABLES	RESULTS	INTREPRETATION
PERCEIVED EFFECTS OF NEW NORMAL APPROACH IN EDUCATION		
Fostering Relationships	0.882	Good
Engagement	0.912	Excellent
Timeliness	0.905	Excellent
Communications	0.862	Good
Technology	0.921	Excellent
Organization	0.901	Excellent
Flexibility	0.908	Excellent
FACTORS AFFECTING THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE		
Time	0.911	Excellent
Learning Environment	0.910	Excellent
Peer Support	0.898	Good

Proper Guidance	0.898	Good
Family Resources	0.866	Good

Quantitative analysis of the data gathered from the research instruments focused on the use of percentages and comparison of statistical treatment. To sum – up, the table below shows the source of data to answer the objectives of the study and the statistical tools to be used.

Table 3. Matrix of Analysis

OBJECTIVES	SOURCE DATA	OF /	ANALYSIS TOOL
1. Know the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:			
1.1 Gender			
1.2 Year Level			
1.3 Students' Status	Part 1	/	Frequency
1.4 Geographical Location during Online Classes	Demographic Profile		Percentage
1.5 Internet Connection Provider	Instrument		
1.6 Mobile Devices Used			
2. Identify the perceived effects of the new normal approach in education to the respondents based on:			
2.1 Fostering Relationship	Part 2	/	Weighted Mean
2.2 Engagement	Perceived Effects		
2.3 Timeliness	Questionnaire		
2.4 Communication			Ranking
2.5 Technology			
2.6 Organization			
2.7 Flexibility			
3. Determine the factors that influence the productivity level and academic performance of the respondents in conducting new normal approach in education:			
3.1 Time			Weighted Mean
3.2 Learning Environment	Part 3	/	Factor
3.3 Peer Support	Questionnaire		
3.4 Proper Guidance			
3.5 Family Resources			Ranking

- | | |
|---|-----------------|
| 4. Assess if significant relationships exist among the perceived effects of the new normal approach and factors influence the productivity level and academic performance | Spearman
Rho |
| 5. Ascertain if there a significant difference on respondents' perceived effects of new normal approach when grouped according to their demographic profiles. | ANOVA |

Statistical data

Table 4. Interpretation of Values

SCALE	MEAN RANGE	INTERPRETATION	EXPLANATION
4	3.50 – 4.00	Strongly Agree	The effects of new normal in education and the factors influence academic performance are highly notice by the respondent.
3	2.50 – 3.49	Agree	The effects of new normal in education and the factors influence academic performance are moderately notice by the respondent.
2	1.50 – 2.49	Disagree	The effects of new normal in education and the factors influence academic performance are slightly notice by the respondent.
1	1.00 – 1.49	Strongly Disagree	The effects of new normal in education and the factors influence academic performance are not totally notice by the respondent.

RESULTS

In order to complete this study appropriately, the data collected has to be examined in order to respond to the research questions. Data is interpreted descriptively as already shown in previous chapter. This part involves investigating, presenting and interpreting of findings resulting from this study. Data analysis and interpretation are done. This is based on the survey's outcome and conducts a quantitative analysis of data involved.

Table 5. Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Female	65	48
Male	70	52
	1032	

Total	135	100
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Table 6. Year Level

Year Level	Frequency	Percentage
1 st Year	35	25.9
2 nd Year	56	41.5
3 rd Year	44	32.6
Total	135	100

Table 7. Academic Status

Student Status	Frequency	Percentage
Regular	122	90.4
Irregular (Returnee)	6	4.4
Irregular (Transferee)	7	5.2
Total	135	100

Table 8. Geographic Location

Geographical Location	Frequency	Percentage
NCR	1	0.7
Cavite	4	3.0
Laguna	82	60.7
Batangas	28	20.7
Rizal	7	0.7
Quezon	14	10.4
Others / Bicol / Mindoro	5	3.7
Total	135	100

Table 9. Internet Connection

Internet Connection	Frequency	Percentage
DSL	14	10.4
Cable	24	17.8
Fiber	75	55.6
Wireless	18	13.3
Broadband	4	3.0
Total	135	100

Table 10. Perceived Effects of New Normal

Perceived Effects of New Normal in Education	Composite Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Over-all Ranking
Fostering relationships	3.05	Agree	3.5
Engagement	3.04	Agree	5

Timeliness	2.96	Agree	7
Communications	3.07	Agree	1.5
Technology	3.05	Agree	3.5
Organization	3.01	Agree	6
Flexibility	3.07	Agree	1.5

Legend: 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49 Disagree; 2.50-3.49 Agree; 3.50-4.00 Strongly Agree

Table 11. Factors affecting the Productivity Level and Academic Performances

Factors affecting the Productivity Level and Academic Performance	Composite Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Over-all Ranking
Time Management	3.12	Agree	3.5
Learning Environment	3.14	Agree	2
Peer Support	3.17	Agree	1
Proper Guidance	3.05	Agree	5
Family Resources	3.12	Agree	3.5

Legend: 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49 Disagree; 2.50-3.49 Agree; 3.50-4.00 Strongly Agree

Table 12. Perceived effects of New Normal Approach based on Fostering Relationships

FOSTERING RELATIONSHIPS	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. The new normal in education provides me a venue where the students and teachers are in group and are active in significant way	3.07	Agree	5
2. In online set-up, the teachers consider my personal presence in class and he / she checked my attention to details and interaction as important in answering the discussion questions.	3.24	Agree	2
3. The teachers are engaged, relational, and personal in communication with me like in normal classrooms that makes my interactions lead to higher – learning level so I could expand to my peers and classmates.	3.13	Agree	3
4. Social interactions are emphasized in our virtual classes by means of learning facilitation methods like open communication, productive interactions, and cohesions between me and with my peers / classmates.	3.09	Agree	4
5. The learning activities during our online classes create an atmosphere in which make me feel close to my classmates, peers, and teachers.	2.93	Agree	7
6. I do not see the online platforms as major obstacle to effective interactions because I have close contacts with my teachers, classmates, and peers through smaller group lessons and less longer lectures.	2.86	Agree	8
7. In every online classes, I feel into the real classrooms in a way that I could communicate effectively with my teachers and classmates through more frequent contacts, detailed instructions, and actionable participations in online venue like Teams, Zooms, Group Chats, and the likes.	2.73	Agree	9
8. My relationships with my teachers and classmates develop ties and motivations that make me succeed to finish all academic requirements.	3.02	Agree	6

3. During our online classes, there are fixed schedules but with a great deal of flexibility and I could be able to set my own timetable to complete the course works.	3.09	Agree	1
4. Knowing the schedules for synchronous and asynchronous sessions as part of course orientation on first day of class, I do not encounter any difficulties in following the class schedules and dates of the requirement submissions.	3.03	Agree	2
5. Since I attended the virtual class at my home, my time seems versatile and I could easily find ways to reconcile with a structured schedule.	2.97	Agree	5
6. Even though I used computers (laptops, notepad, mobile phone) during online classes, I could finish my course tasks on-time because I do not allow some unnecessary activities to distract me like surfing the net, search social network sites or watch latest viral video online.	2.91	Agree	7
7. This new normal allows me to put break between the period of studying and it can help me to focus, allows myself free from distraction, and helps me to finish my classes efficiently.	2.86	Agree	8
8. The use of online platforms in this new normal make me able to fulfill my other obligations and personal commitments.	2.99	Agree	3
9. In online learning, I could be able to use most of my time effectively rather than regular face to face classes happened in the actual classrooms.	2.84	Agree	9
Composite mean	2.96	Agree	

Legend: 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49 Disagree; 2.50-3.49 Agree; 3.50-4.00 Strongly Agree

Table 15. Perceived effects of New Normal Approach based on Communication

COMMUNICATION	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Using online platforms during classes, I can be able to communicate more openly with my teachers and classmates because of greater versatility in conversations.	2.96	Agree	9
2. As I used the digital media to learn, I together with my classmates and teachers could be able to transmit our ideas to one another more clearly either in voice call or in text forms.	3.03	Agree	7
3. Asynchronous and synchronous classes give the opportunities that enable me to create a healthy online environment for communication and collaboration.	3.06	Agree	5
4. Lessons are mostly transmitted using the electronic and media technology, and it support my learning experience because of online materials which can be access anytime.	3.07	Agree	3
5. The online delivery of classes supports and enhances both learning and teaching as interaction between me and my teachers keeps on-going even after the classes.	3.06	Agree	5
6. My teachers and classmates have considered the web-based communication instruments like messengers in FB, Teams, or LMS as powerful ways of helping me to develop my own information through interactions and vice versa.	3.16	Agree	2

7. While using various online platforms, I could be able to understand well the message of course announcements and activity instructions that are posted online in LMS or the likes by my teachers.	3.06	Agree	5
8. Since most of the conversations are in online form, I send responses to my teachers and classmates in good correspondence by reviewing the composition of my message first before delivering it to them.	3.19	Agree	1
9. My capacity and capability toward the learning cycles are better this online learning period because I could access my teachers and classmates easier.	3.01	Agree	8
Composite mean	3.07	Agree	

Legend: 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49 Disagree; 2.50-3.49 Agree; 3.50-4.00 Strongly Agree

Table 16. Perceived effects of New Normal Approach based on Technology

TECHNOLOGY	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. With the proliferation of the online classes, my learning capabilities are already beginning to shift due to the advent of present technology in positive ways and beneficial on my part.	3.09	Agree	2
2. With the help of technology, this new normal in education makes my learning more into wide range and no longer limited to just corners of the classroom.	2.98	Agree	9
3. I could learn faster as emerging technology finds its way into classrooms during online classes because if some lessons are not clear to me, I could search it right away.	3.00	Agree	8
4. Since internet connections and mobile devices are essentials in the conduct of online classes, these technological products have positive impacts in improving my studying like more access to research websites and other electronic sources.	3.06	Agree	5
5. Mobile technology promotes access to information and increasing my dedication to learning because I only visit the websites that are necessary to my lessons.	3.04	Agree	6
6. The teachers use the abilities of mobile technology and applications more and much frequently during online classes and it enhances my learning practices.	3.10	Agree	1
7. Mobile learning (M-learning) as part of the new normal in education has become an important aspect of educational technology because it helps me to read, interact, and exchange ideas with each other.	3.08	Agree	4
8. Connecting in an online learning material like lessons, video discussions, and activities that are posted by my teachers in virtual platform will let me have a flexible access.	3.09	Agree	3
9. This new normal in education encourages interactive works and cooperation on my part through simultaneous contacts with my classmates and teachers in terms group work development with the use of mobile devices.	3.04	Agree	7
Composite mean	3.05	Agree	

Legend: 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49 Disagree; 2.50-3.49 Agree; 3.50-4.00 Strongly Agree

Table 17. Perceived effects of New Normal Approach based on Organization

ORGANIZATION	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. The conduct of online classes makes me incorporate some additional activities in my daily routine like contemplating classes / sessions, reviewing the reading materials, and concentrating to study.	3.10	Agree	2
2. This new normal in educations improves my learning experience by developing and applying viable study habits because I do not necessarily require to prepare my things going to school.	3.01	Agree	5
3. Since I spent most of my times at our home during the online classes, I have more spare time to clean and organize my stuffs essential to my study.	3.07	Agree	3
4. Because most of my course requirements are in soft copy forms, I had developed ways on how to search or retrieve them easily once I need it.	3.17	Agree	1
5. At least 15 minutes before my online class schedules, I am ready physically and mentally, and all things needed on the said class like laptops, pens, and notes are ready.	3.03	Agree	4
6. My study area during this new normal are cleaner and much organize compare during there is actual residential sessions at the school.	2.93	Agree	7
7. My study habits are more improved on this new normal in such a way I religiously follow my planned activities compare the previous years.	2.93	Agree	6
8. I have sufficient time in a day to complete all my requirements in every class because I have a timetable to follow in consistent manner.	2.92	Agree	8
9. In this new normal, I can concentrate peacefully and alone in normal times, read the lesson or material, and review notes before taking the exam or performance tasks.	2.91	Agree	9
Composite mean	3.01	Agree	

Legend: 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49 Disagree; 2.50-3.49 Agree; 3.50-4.00 Strongly Agree

Table 18. Perceived effects of New Normal Approach based on Flexibility

FLEXIBILITY	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. This new normal in education provides me with flexible learning opportunities like teachers understand the students' differences and I have choices in various degree about what, where, when, why, and how to learn.	3.05	Agree	5
2. Blended learning is one of the approaches in this new normal and it helps me to set suitable learning objectives and be accountable on my own learning.	3.07	Agree	4
3. Flexible learning facilitates customized learning wherein my desires, preferences, experiences, and style of learning are put into considerations and I could feel the student-centered approach.	3.04	Agree	8
4. In this new approach in education, I experience the versatility of the online learning because I could monitor the learning operation and track my actions in LMS.	3.11	Agree	1

5. Online learning helps the student to learn at their own pace because my teachers can tailor the content and delivery according to my needs and background.	3.04	Agree	9
6. Because of new normal, there are clear standards or policies to follow regarding some challenges like students with restricted access in internet and I am aware of it.	3.05	Agree	6
7. The new approach in education helps me to learn the “must know learning” while at the same time I could ably plan my future activities at my own pace.	3.05	Agree	7
8. Once my teachers set the due dates for the submission of requirements, I planned well my time to possibly finish all of them and set priority list.	3.11	Agree	2
9. If there are valid reasons and I cannot comply with the due dates; I did not hesitate to inform my teachers and my teachers are willing to evaluate my situations so we could meet halfway.	3.10	Agree	3
Composite mean	3.07	Agree	

Legend: 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49 Disagree; 2.50-3.49 Agree; 3.50-4.00 Strongly Agree

Table 19. Summary of the Respondents’ Perceived Effects of New Normal Approach in Education

Perceived Effects of New Normal in Education	Composite Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Over-all Ranking
Fostering relationships	3.05	Agree	3.5
Engagement	3.04	Agree	5
Timeliness	2.96	Agree	7
Communications	3.07	Agree	1.5
Technology	3.05	Agree	3.5
Organization	3.01	Agree	6
Flexibility	3.07	Agree	1.5

Legend: 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49 Disagree; 2.50-3.49 Agree; 3.50-4.00 Strongly Agree

Table 20. Time Management as factors affecting the Respondents’ Productivity Level and Academic Performance

TIME MANAGEMENT	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I could get an outstanding grade for my course requirements if I do things in order of priority and accomplish what needs to be done based on my timetable.	3.20	Agree	2
2. I could submit excellent requirement if I always get activities done on time that makes me feel that use time effectively.	3.25	Agree	1
3. I tackle difficult performance tasks or summative exams without procrastinating because I spend enough time for planning or force myself to make time for planning.	3.03	Agree	9
4. As I received the mechanics for Outcome Evaluation, Performance Task, and Summative Exams, I started to prepare a daily or weekly “to do” list and prioritize my list in order of importance, not urgency.	3.13	Agree	4
5. I am able to meet deadlines without rushing in the last minute and keep up-to-date on my readings and homework assignments.	3.07	Agree	7

6. I spend enough time on academic matters by prevent interruptions to distract me and avoid devoting too much time in insignificant matters.	3.04	Agree	8
7. I have weekly schedules on which I record fixed commitments such as synchronous class and asynchronous sessions and I plan time to relax and be with my friends also.	3.12	Agree	5
8. I try to do the most important activities like Performance Tasks accomplishment and Summative Exams preparation during the most energetic periods of the day and periodically re-assess my activities in relation to my academic goals.	3.14	Agree	3
9. I have a clear idea of what I want to accomplish during the academic term and judge myself by accomplishments of tasks rather than the amount of activity or “busy-ness”	3.10	Agree	6
Composite mean	3.12	Agree	

Legend: 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49 Disagree; 2.50-3.49 Agree; 3.50-4.00 Strongly Agree

Table 21. Learning Environment as factors affecting the Respondents’ Productivity Level and Academic Performance

LEARNING ENVIRONMENT	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I can be able to finish my course tasks beyond average if my teachers have good relationship with me and I can see smartness, confidence, and firmness in making decisions on him / her.	3.17	Agree	1
2. I can be able to get an outstanding grade if my teachers are open to suggestions / opinions, are worthy of praise, and have appealing personalities with good sense of humor.	3.16	Agree	3
3. I can be able to submit best requirements / activities if my teachers imposed proper discipline and is not lenient in following the prescribed rules set by the school.	3.16	Agree	3
4. I can be able to tackle difficult course activities without rushing if I have a smooth and organized study / working area	3.15	Agree	5
5. I can be able to create excellent performance tasks and to get high ratings in examinations if there are available visual aids, workbooks, and reading materials during online classes.	3.12	Agree	9
6. To accomplish the course tasks, I rely most of the time on the explanations of the objectives of the activities and presentations of updated trends relevant to the subject matters.	3.13	Agree	6
7. A well-organized subject matter which are systematically following the course plan helps me to prepare an exceptional output for every course.	3.16	Agree	3
8. Utilization of various strategies, teaching aid / devices and techniques in presenting the lessons assist me to aim for high grades.	3.13	Agree	7.5
9. I could able to finish all requirements on time if the class time and activities are well-planned because it supports my problem solving and critical thinking skills.	3.13	Agree	7.5
Composite mean	3.14	Agree	

Legend: 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49 Disagree; 2.50-3.49 Agree; 3.50-4.00 Strongly Agree

Table 22. Peer Support as factors affecting the Respondents' Productivity Level and Academic Performance

PEER SUPPORT	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. My teachers and classmates give details regarding the different school activities or works that supports me to develop my motivations and engagement to accomplish the course tasks.	3.15	Agree	1
2. I consider the emotional support and security coming from my family members and friends in aiming to finish all requirements and get exceptional ratings.	3.18	Agree	3
3. Having cooperative learning with peers like giving course plan and give chance to work on teamwork skills improve my academic performance and able me to accomplish the performance tasks and activities.	3.19	Agree	3
4. Through peer-to-peer support / collaboration, I could easily complete my course requirements rather than work alone.	3.16	Agree	5
5. Getting people help midst of obstacles and difficult tasks makes me becomes more competitive and encourage to stay on my degree program.	3.18	Agree	9
6. Having a support from teachers and classmates supply me a thinking that I can count on others during difficult times and I can finish my works excellently.	3.21	Agree	6
7. I think about the assistance extended by the School Administrators and Staff like Dean and PC conference as great aid to lessen the difficulties during the online classes.	3.11	Agree	3
8. I grab the opportunity of groupworks' activities because it allows me to form relationships and develop sense of responsibility which I might not typically engaged with during online classes.	3.15	Agree	7.5
9. I like to provide supportive environment through sharing of experience and demonstrating personal commitment to successfully completing the course works.	3.19	Agree	7.5
Composite mean	3.17	Agree	

Legend: 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49 Disagree; 2.50-3.49 Agree; 3.50-4.00 Strongly Agree

Table 23. Proper Guidance as factors affecting the Respondents' Productivity Level and Academic Performance

PROPER GUIDANCE	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Once I am experiencing issues and trouble related to academic matters, I rely most of the time for my parents' help and assistance to accomplish my course tasks.	2.99	Agree	8
2. At home, my parents and family members have arrangement of technology and other learning materials to upgrade my academic performance.	3.07	Agree	4
3. The emotional support from my teachers and family members contributes to my wellbeing which helps me to participate during online classes and synchronous sessions.	3.07	Agree	4
4. As student, it made me feel least likely to attend the online classes because of the transitions of new normal in education but the parental and family supports are relevant for me to cope up with the transitions.	3.07	Agree	4

5. My mentalities and study habits that correspond to academic accomplishments are improved because of the guidance given by the people around me like family members and friend.	3.04	Agree	6
6. I performed well in the test and examinations since my parents properly guide me by simply giving advices and word of wisdom.	2.98	Agree	9
7. The execution of my performance tasks and outcome evaluations are greatly influence by the way my teachers guide me.	3.13	Agree	1
8. My teachers repeat the concepts, class requirements and course work instructions when I have hard time to learn so I could obtain complete comprehensions of the idea.	3.10	Agree	2
9. My parents' answers for troubles, supported, and provisions on giving help me especially on difficult times of online classes.	3.02	Agree	7
Composite mean	3.05	Agree	

Legend: 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49 Disagree; 2.50-3.49 Agree; 3.50-4.00 Strongly Agree

Table 24. Family Resources as factors affecting the Respondents' Productivity Level and Academic Performance

FAMILY RESOURCES	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. The socio-economic factors like family income, parents' education and the likes have influence on my academic performance.	3.18	Agree	1
2. I can be able to produce better outcomes if my parents could be able to provide me all essential things for online classes	3.13	Agree	6
3. I could perform better at online classes because my parents are financially capacitated and give moral support.	3.10	Agree	7
4. I can finish my academic requirements smoothly every term because my family are able to support all my needs.	3.14	Agree	4.5
5. My academic performance is influence by my attitude and behaviors coming from my family social and cultural resources that we can use to cope with difficult situations.	3.17	Agree	2
6. I think that continuing-generation students (with at least one parent with a bachelor's degree) are gain more support which contribute to academic performance.	3.15	Agree	3
7. My parents' participation during online classes (simply watching me and slightly listening) make me more focus on my academic performance.	2.96	Agree	9
8. My parents are wellsprings of resources which give a security especially on difficult times of online classes.	3.10	Agree	8
9. I could do all needed requirements during online classes and I consider my family resources as great contributors on my academic performance.	3.14	Agree	4.5
Composite mean	3.12	Agree	

Legend: 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49 Disagree; 2.50-3.49 Agree; 3.50-4.00 Strongly Agree

Table 25. Summary of the Factors Affecting the Productivity Level and Academic Performance

Factors affecting the Productivity Level and Academic Performance	Composite Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Over-all Ranking
Time Management	3.12	Agree	3.5

Learning Environment	3.14	Agree	2
Peer Support	3.17	Agree	1
Proper Guidance	3.05	Agree	5
Family Resources	3.12	Agree	3.5

Legend: 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49 Disagree; 2.50-3.49 Agree; 3.50-4.00 Strongly Agree

Table 26. Significant Relationship between Time Management and Perceived Effects of New Normal Approach

Variables	r-value	p-value	Interpretation
Time vs Fostering relationships	.599	.000	Significant
Time vs Engagement	.630	.000	Significant
Time vs Timeliness	.666	.000	Significant
Time vs Communications	.692	.000	Significant
Time vs Technology	.682	.000	Significant
Time vs Organization	.665	.000	Significant
Time vs Flexibility	.686	.000	Significant

Legend: If the p-value is <.05, Significant. If the p-value is >.05, Not Significant

Table 27. Significant Relationship between Learning Environment and Perceived Effects of New Normal Approach

Variables	r-value	p-value	Interpretation
Learning Environment vs Fostering relationships	.585	.000	Significant
Learning Environment vs Engagement	.576	.000	Significant
Learning Environment vs Timeliness	.650	.000	Significant
Learning Environment vs Communications	.728	.000	Significant
Learning Environment vs Technology	.622	.000	Significant
Learning Environment vs Organization	.614	.000	Significant
Learning Environment vs Flexibility	.751	.000	Significant

Legend: If the p-value is <.05, Significant. If the p-value is >.05, Not Significant.

Table 28. Significant Relationship between Peer Support and Perceived Effects of New Normal Approach

Variables	r-value	p-value	Interpretation
Peer support vs Fostering relationships	.525	.000	Significant
Peer support vs Engagement	.616	.000	Significant
Peer support vs Timeliness	.600	.000	Significant
Peer support vs Communications	.734	.000	Significant
Peer support vs Technology	.611	.000	Significant
Peer support vs Organization	.583	.000	Significant
Peer support vs Flexibility	.711	.000	Significant

Legend: If the p-value is <.05, Significant. If the p-value is >.05, Not Significant.

Table 29. Significant Relationship between Proper Guidance and Perceived Effects of New Normal Approach

Variables	r-value	p-value	Interpretation
Proper guidance vs Fostering relationships	.478	.000	Significant
Proper guidance vs Engagement	.590	.000	Significant
Proper guidance vs Timeliness	.608	.000	Significant
Proper guidance vs Communications	.724	.000	Significant
Proper guidance vs Technology	.707	.000	Significant
Proper guidance vs Organization	.680	.000	Significant
Proper guidance vs Flexibility	.729	.000	Significant

Legend: If the p-value is <.05, Significant. If the p-value is >.05, Not Significant.

Table 30. Significant Relationship between Family Resources and Perceived Effects of New Normal Approach

Variables	r-value	p-value	Interpretation
Family resources vs Fostering relationships	.482	.000	Significant
Family resources vs Engagement	.581	.000	Significant
Family resources vs Timeliness	.612	.000	Significant
Family resources vs Communications	.679	.000	Significant
Family resources vs Technology	.625	.000	Significant
Family resources vs Organization	.631	.000	Significant
Family resources vs Flexibility	.672	.000	Significant

Legend: If the p-value is <.05, Significant. If the p-value is >.05, Not Significant.

Table 31. Significant Differences on Respondents Perceived Effect when grouped according to Sex

Perceived effects	f-value	p-value	Interpretation
Fostering relationships	.339	.562	Not Significant
Engagement	.063	.803	Not Significant
Timeliness	.742	.390	Not Significant
Communications	.735	.393	Not Significant
Technology	.727	.395	Not Significant
Organization	2.030	.157	Not Significant
Flexibility	1.359	.246	Not Significant

Legend: If the p-value is <.05, Significant. If the p-value is >.05, Not Significant.

Table 32. Significant Differences on Respondents Perceived Effect when grouped according to Year Level

Perceived effects	f-value	p-value	Interpretation
Fostering relationships	.111	.895	Not Significant
Engagement	.504	.605	Not Significant
Timeliness	.040	.961	Not Significant
Communications	.202	.818	Not Significant
Technology	.279	.757	Not Significant

Organization	.302	.740	Not Significant
Flexibility	.269	.764	Not Significant

Legend: If the p-value is <.05, Significant. If the p-value is >.05, Not Significant.

Table 33. Significant Differences on Respondents Perceived Effect when grouped according to Students' Status

Perceived effects	f-value	p-value	Interpretation
Fostering relationships	.164	.849	Not Significant
Engagement	.617	.541	Not Significant
Timeliness	.796	.453	Not Significant
Communications	.456	.635	Not Significant
Technology	.547	.580	Not Significant
Organization	.676	.510	Not Significant
Flexibility	1.025	.362	Not Significant

Legend: If the p-value is <.05, Significant. If the p-value is >.05, Not Significant.

Table 34. Significant Differences on Respondents Perceived Effect when grouped according to Students' Geographical Location

Perceived effects	f-value	p-value	Interpretation
Fostering relationships	.388	.886	Not Significant
Engagement	.612	.720	Not Significant
Timeliness	.762	.601	Not Significant
Communications	1.017	.418	Not Significant
Technology	1.197	.312	Not Significant
Organization	.851	.533	Not Significant
Flexibility	1.195	.313	Not Significant

Legend: If the p-value is <.05, Significant. If the p-value is >.05, Not Significant.

Table 35. Significant Differences on Respondents Perceived Effect when grouped according to Students' Internet Connections

Perceived effects	f-value	p-value	Interpretation
Fostering relationships	.194	.941	Not Significant
Engagement	.211	.932	Not Significant
Timeliness	.307	.873	Not Significant
Communications	.071	.991	Not Significant
Technology	.479	.751	Not Significant
Organization	.328	.859	Not Significant
Flexibility	.186	.946	Not Significant

Legend: If the p-value is <.05, Significant. If the p-value is >.05, Not Significant.

Table 36. Significant Differences on Respondents Perceived Effect when grouped according to Students' Mobile Devices used

Perceived effects	f-value	p-value	Interpretation
Fostering relationships	.480	.620	Not Significant
Engagement	.307	.736	Not Significant
Timeliness	1.087	.340	Not Significant
Communications	.160	.852	Not Significant
Technology	.600	.550	Not Significant
Organization	2.091	.128	Not Significant
Flexibility	.816	.445	Not Significant

Legend: If the p-value is <.05, Significant. If the p-value is >.05, Not Significant.

DISCUSSION

Sex was included by the researchers in the study because of some methodological concerns. The differentiation between respondents' perceptions will be very significant once the group is split along this line. Also, it created a level playing field for individual opinions as the participants were an equal number of males and females. In table 6, 65 females and 70 males that constituted 48% and 52% respectively participated in the study. This means that there was little dominance from male participants. This result agrees with Dierdorff (2020) article which states that male to female ratio for Philippines is 100.87 males per 100 females. Male to female ratio of Philippines rose from 98.91 males per 100 females' in 1950 to 100.87 males per 100 females in 2020 growing at an average annual rate of only about a tenth of one percent every year. This also indicates that Philippines is one of those places where gender parity in education might come soonest or has already been reached; hence there are small noticeable gaps between boys' and girls' enrolment rates unlike many other nations across Asia where such disparities still persist till date. Actually, almost equal number of students who took part in this study were male or female ones. That resulted to diversity including balance and perspective contributing to improved quality as well as social relevance of researches carried out on them

The level of year refers to four years of college, freshman, and sophomore, junior and senior. It is not the number of years you have spent in college that classifies students but the amount of semester hours which you have earned. In this research it was important to understand the student level since they had different experiences in attending face to face classes and online learning. Since every year level has their own experience or background into a new normal approach in education therefor researchers included year level as part of demographic profile to know about their views on "new normal" approach towards education. Similarly, understanding the perceptions for students at each grade would be good starting point for achieving that objective.

One of the demographic profiles in this study included student status which aims at determining regulars, irregulars (returnees) and irregular (transferees) perspectives. For instance, when talking about preference it will help also see the difference between

regular students and irregular ones like for scheduling environment etc. The result shows that there are exactly one hundred twenty-two regular students; six are returning back to school after dropping out while seven transferred to public schools all totaling to one hundred thirty-five students. This indicates more regular than non-regular ones. As many as there are who count themselves as regulars so there are enrolled in these courses who do not consider them as such because they are simply coming to learn. When motivated to learn, according to Hirudayaraj & McLean (2018), students become competent and confident with their skills. Additionally, practical effects motivate them further rendering them engaged learners. Therefore teachers who work hard with every learner's motivation can manage educational objectives: student achievement and continuous learning. On the other hand according to Favour (2017), irregular students frequently confront several difficulties in their academic subjects. The gravity of the matter is like a kind of simple difficulty experienced before. A simple problem that can be encountered is having a confusing or conflicting class schedule. To sum-up, the study was dominated by the perceptions of regular students. This means that the data generated was merely on the point of view of the regular students which is much acceptable.

As one of the demographic profiles in this research, the researchers featured on geographical location among several others. The researchers need to know and identify where the respondents which is students having their online educations. This means that student's location during distance learning could be in Manila, CALABARZON or any other places where he manages it from, performs it in and interacts on an internet platform or elsewhere. The results presented in table 9 indicated that sixty percent were from Laguna area followed by Batangas with twenty-seven percent then Quezon accounted for ten point four percent. Such a huge domination exists between southern regions over northern part region. Dyer, et.al (2018) stated attending college close to home saves a lot of money, gives you more internship and networking opportunities, makes it easy in case of an emergency.

To get access to the Internet, an Internet service provider is needed. Internet service providers (ISPs) serve as intermediaries between users and networks providing global connectivity. The majority of ISPs offer broadband internet access via cable lines, DSL lines or fiber optic cables. Even if you use a public Wi-Fi signal to connect your device online; yet still this Wi-Fi router is connected with an ISP which offers internet service through it. In light of current study was conducted based on the term internet connection because now having internet connection provides access to a vast amount of information, expertise, and educational opportunities. For instance, professors use online resources to plan lessons while students use them for skills development. "Internet connection" was one of several demographic variables that could easily relate students with teachers by using it as a medium or bridge in online education. Also, students can find assignments, quizzes and presentations as well as any other information related to their studies through the internet. It is shown in Table 10 that fiber connections are still leading with 55.6% and followed closely by cable network (17.8%) while wireless connectivity takes third place with 13.3%. This means that Fiber Connection has huge gap between the two followed. The result correspondence with the website fusionconnect (2018) stating fiber-optic internet services are quicker, with speeds of at least 250-1,000

Mbps in both directions. Fiber networks provide a more stable network option when compared to other network connections since they are less likely to be disrupted than other types of connectivity. In other words service is guaranteed under fiber networks.

Information and communication technology (ICT) are rapidly being used in educational activities as a teaching and learning aid, in keeping with this trend. As supported by Gomez (2016), this is due to the advantages of mobile learning, which include the ability to exchange knowledge without regard to distance or time constraints, the ability to encourage the development of critical thinking, participatory learning, problem solving, and lifelong communication skills. On this study, researchers used term mobile devices because these are the common tools used in online learning especially in this time of pandemic. Also, students can use mobile devices as a tool in finding relevant information regarding their projects and assignments, as well as seek advice from other researchers while they save and arrange their research materials on computers. The researchers included Mobile Devices as one of the demographic profiles to differentiate the mobile devices used in taking the new normal approach. In distant education, the mobile device is gradually becoming a compelling learning tool for enhancing teaching and learning. Its use allows for more flexible course delivery, as well as learners' access to online learning platforms, course resources, and digital interaction. The table 11 shows that the computer or laptop is the most useful device in online learning with fifty nine and three percentage, followed by smartphone or android with thirty five and six percentage and the least device used in online learning is Ipad with five and two percentage. The study shows that the computer or laptop dominates the survey with a 59.3 percent. This leads that the computer/laptop is the most used and most helpful mobile device during the new normal approach to get the schoolwork's finished. The computer has had a significant impact on social progress and is now considered a necessity in today's world. Students can attend classes from anywhere in the globe as long as they have access to a computer and an Internet connection. Also, mobile device has the potential to transform education by bringing in a new style of connected instruction. This concept connects teachers to their students as well as professional knowledge, tools, and systems to assist them in improving their own education and personalizing learning.

Various authors agree that a classroom relationship is vital for success; simultaneously, according to many authors, the most important thing in the classroom for success is good interpersonal relationships. When a student builds connections with their peers and classmates, they become more likely to engage in studies hence this could lead to top academic achievements. It was also noticed that behavioral problems were significantly reduced due to positive interaction (Reese, 2015). In terms of researchers' evaluation, there were no other indicators except agree. It means that even if instruction was done through distance learning mode online class behavior towards each other remained quite respectful which means it went well. However, there was no such indicator interpreted as strongly agreed. Similarly, this is just an initial step considering that schools are still attempting to get their feet wet regarding online classes. Mostly, the quality of education lies squarely on how teachers relate with students all through the learning process. This posed a significant challenge to educators in guiding their pupils into realizing their educational potential. To boost student participation in online learning environments researches have shown that; the more they pay attention to developing

positive teacher-student relationships (Pope, 2016). In summary effects of new normal approach on education are seen through fostering relationships and its composite mean is therefore considered as agree (3.05). Subsequently this indicates some strengths and weaknesses about an online class involvement. However; one may look deeper into this because approximately half of the total indicators had strongly agreed interpretations although it does not guarantee high quality of instructions at all times. Dyer et al. (2018) postulate that social interaction teaching methods foster learning communities. The curriculum and teaching methodology are important to make it successful. Nevertheless, for any online program's curriculum it should be well scrutinized and prepared before being launched. In building online education programs in a rush, many institutions ignore the value of curriculum content development as well as the need for competent individuals who could produce it for them. However, what works for a classroom in terms of curriculum design or instruction may not necessarily work for an online setting since learning and instructional paradigms are very distinct in such cases (Akamai, 2017). Consequently; using texts communication along with group interaction and participation should be considered while developing online syllabus.

The suspension of face to face classes due to the pandemic has also made it difficult for lecturers to tell whether their students are still involved in what they are teaching because they can only see their students on their monitor and they can only be observed once they have online classes. Based on the researcher's evaluation as per verbal interpretation, all interpretations were agree. Based on verbal interpretation evaluation done by researchers, all the interpretations gathered agreed. Furthermore, having an interpretation that agrees is a positive result from respondents because despite of shifting into online classes within a year, the learners remain involved in learning. Therefore, to sum up everything, according to perceptions of engagement as effects of new normal method in education, composite mean is 3.04 meaning agree. This new approach gives teachers a different way to understand their students; it will help them keep student focus and engagement without losing any more interest since it is no longer traditional face-to-face classes anymore. In relation to this matter, this strategy helps students; again I would like to emphasize that it is important for those who talk industry experts among others through webinars. Through this means the students were able to see how they could apply what they had learned in school so that they can become better engaged learners when given future industry companies opportunities. Still many times these people insist on calling themselves professionals instead of individuals that work professionally with other people's lives. As Soffer, et.al (2017) noted that active participation and engagement should be integrated into making lessons or activities and this has been supported by statements therein. One approach which may be used as one of the most effective methods towards achieving interactive lessons is using interactive lessons instead.

One of the most important things to consider when taking an online course or remote classes is time planning because students are responsible for directing their own learning and progress. In order to learn online, they must allocate time to revisit and go through the lessons. It turns out that everything in oral interpretation agrees with each other. Based on what respondents said, all the results of indicators are positively stated. This could be considered as a fairly good beginning since they have just been done online

and can be greatly improved over time. In addition, it took 2.96 composite mean in terms of timeliness as perceived effects of new normal method on education which means agree. They are aware of how to make a schedule; they understand how to make proper use of their time so that every minute counts for them and helps them achieve more within short period. Again, this will ensure that every student finishes tasks faster while at the same time giving them enough time for personal activities or hobbies during recess periods even if some students want freedom to choose subjects at school. Thus, timeliness was among the perceived effects of new normal in education with lowest composite mean in this study. As such it should be noted that this should not only focus on personal reasons but also give room for others who might have different motives (Wanner & Palmer, 2015). They do not waste their time aimlessly hence making it possible for them to act upon other crucial things (Fry et al., 2015), except only when certain situations may require a person's attention immediately (Williams, 2017). The right management system also makes it easier for learners to track their academic progression throughout the year including holidays. Students feel less stressed when they know how much progress has been made toward completing assignments because they can see what remains on the list of tasks to be done. Just like that, they complete and become successful in their aims. In addition, it allows more time for students to finish their assignments on time with a great focus on them without any distractions (Hodges and Yarbrough, 2017).

One of the keys to achievement and well-being in a “new normal” approach to education or face-to-face class is communication. According to the researcher's questionnaire, they all agreed on all issues confronting new normal approach. It therefore indicates that New Normal Approach has yielded successful communication within education system. In conclusion, it can be said that “communication as perceived effects of new normal approach in education” had a composite mean of 3.07 and an agreement verbal interpretation. When communication flows easily, work goes much more smoothly. It is hard to finish a task when communication or instruction is difficult. These internet applications can also be used for accessing, sending and saving important files, papers and presentations. With these features at hand, people could show their screen by sharing it with others too. For students who struggle due to poor teacher-student communication ability; learning may be difficult leading to poor academic progress (Morreale and Pearson, 2000). Students must differentiate between correct answers and wrong ones depending on teachers' classroom language skill only. Student during lecture needs to concentrate on his lecturer in order to learn something from him/her. Teachers should offer straight talk which will make sense at the same time. The mentioned works are media in transmitting good communication skills in online environment.

Connected learning is an educational approach that connects teachers with their students, and also professional knowledge, tools and systems to enable teachers' personal growth in education and personalized learning. Therefore, technology has a mean of 3.05 from perceived effects of new normal approach in education and it is interpreted as agree. The results of this survey showed that new normal approach was advantageous to the students and the teachers because it helped them to search and communicate with their peers at a time when pandemic struck globally. E-learning has extended or become an alternative due to attractiveness of mobile devices, internet and

availability of data that has increased significantly over the last years. This is different across countries or regions where they are applied like in developed nations compared to developing ones (Magulod, 2019). Also in mobile learning optimistic attitude towards adoption can be successfully transferred. The level satisfaction from using m-learning directly depends on perceived assistance received. By providing technological conditions for users and by giving them required prompt, contextual support from specialists these learners will not only gain confidence in m-learning but will also accept it and use it willingly. Therefore through the application of technology, group works as well as wide-range learning outside the classroom characterize conducting online class via online lessons/lectures. This agrees with an article posted on technical education website which states that traditional learning formats may not have flexibility neither provide learning support found in digital learning tools though. Educators are able to introduce more tailored changes into different interactions taking place within their classrooms through employing mobile devices such as computers networked systems for each student's benefit. Digital resources represent games websites and digital books produced for various types of learners starting from novices up to professionals at higher levels involving them into more engaging activities. Learners who have little understanding can approach the experience as a beginner and become intermediate ones as they improve their knowledge and skills

However, the most important thing for the organizational system is that it should prioritize clear communication of objectives and expectations, as well as visibility into the effort required to achieve learning objectives. And it has to be done in such a way that is just as well-organized as the learners themselves. The best virtual setup captures useful and relevant information from student interactions on digital platform and present it through a neat structure with logical flows that are easy to navigate and follow for students. All participants' responses were identified under agree according to researchers. It thus means managing an online class has good organizational effects; moreover both management and student are organized when doing distance learning. But no one scored high legend which was strongly agree. In this case, this means not all systems of an online class are properly structured because distant learning has only started lately and many improvements will be made here to make sure it became fully organized. In conclusion, organization as perceived effect of new normal approach in education composite mean is 3.01 interpreted by agree. According to Sanchez (2020), any course management strategy demands strong syllabus, clear instructions, well-designed materials, timely feedback - whether face-to-face or online teaching approaches.

Through flexible learning, students can determine when and how they will learn by adjusting their course to their specific needs. It means that they retain a lot of information with better results. Also, with flexible online learning, students could take as much time as possible in grasping the subject matter ensuring full knowledge before moving on. This means that students can be doing other activities while taking classes. On the other hand, they have deadlines to meet but more control over how they allocate their time – select time for study, finishing assignments and listening to lectures among others. All these answers went along with agree on the legend said the researchers. This shows that learners become more adaptable to distance education and gain experience using virtual

platforms such as LMS, Google Meet or Zoom Meeting among others. However there were no interpretations for strongly agree, at times when tasks within stipulated periods get hard for one learner thus failing in them whereas one's knowledge is not put into first hand consideration most of the times. According to Paul Drijvers (2016), educational technology has a major advantage because it allows students to go beyond classroom boundaries requiring that learners proceed at their own pace and at levels appropriate for themselves. With online learning systems these practices are supported which also enables progress tracking from both sides i.e., teacher-student perspective through student-teacher ways respectively. They are basically empowering learners so as to learn more easily. That is why monitoring learners' progress in teaching is important but with e-teaching tools used online this becomes not only simple but also efficient enough. Their growth is based on records covering attendance sheets, grades obtained and participation made in LSM (Learning Management System).

Therefore, the study found that both flexibility (3.07) and communication (3.07) were ranked at number one and verbal interpretation of agree based on composite means was got. Thus, it can be said that these variables were the most affected by respondents in transition to new normal in education. As a result relationship building (3.05) and technology (3.05) are tied 3.5 ranked with verbal interpretation of agree as their composite means. This fact shows that when schools rushed to create online learning plans for their students, they had an unexpected opportunity to rethink the structure of the school day itself. Because of this, some institutions chose to have less synchronous class time and more independent, asynchronous time due to lack of resources available for instruction purposes. However, Covarrubias (2015) supported my first point by saying; although many students missed their extracurricular activities at school, others found that fewer planned activities combined with shorter days without commuting resulted in longer sleep periods and more leisure or family time. Engagement with a verbal interpretation of agree ranks at 5 for perceived effects on new normal approach in education according to the authors' explanations (Paris et al., 2019). In other words despite absence of physical schools in place, this new setup still compels students into participating actively in all learning processes as before. Whole class learning is getting facilitated through full-online approaches adopted by students. Flexible term policy with alternative forms of assessment such as open note tests peer review and more revision is redeeming options while engaging learners not only for marks but also because they are learners themselves indicated Paris et al.,(2019). For some pupils who lacked external stimulus though this was particularly hard work is incomplete yet done so far that teachers may use this instance to discuss the importance of learning beyond schooling years and co-design suitable curricula for them to accomplish their tasks.

Time proficiency is a way of considering the weekly calendar and running time for specific purposes in order to work smarter. However, everyone can develop habits or customs that will help them manage their time better, although some individuals take to effective time management more naturally than others. In addition, this will encourage students to be cautious about using their leisure effectively. The statements by all participants fall into the agree area as interpreted by researchers. One would reasonably assume that majority of the learners are still capable of managing their time under online learning circumstances so as to meet subject deadlines. This makes students' day top

priority because they have the choice of prioritizing what needs to be done in a day or prioritizing the most difficult activity or evaluating every project that needs to be worked on and identifying which tasks are the most urgent and necessary ones out of those projects. Nevertheless, no one has been able to reach the higher interpretation, which is a strongly agree. It also means that students who are learning online do not learn all about time management skills because at times they may procrastinate thus missing deadlines and failing courses while other things causing distractions taking place at same instance like having an immediate task that should be done before concentrating on anything else; therefore they end up postponing their duties. Efficient time management does not mean doing more things or doing them quickly but it means doing more important activities each day. Effective time management is actually most essential when compared with efficient time management though student may doubt it sometimes. In case students use their available free space well and submit assignments within timelines, then they can get satisfaction in knowing they did their best. "Students who improve their study habits often become more organized, confident and perform better academically" (Grade Power Learning 2018). This may also enable pupils shun procrastination habit considered dangerous by many because once one starts putting off assignments towards the deadline, there will definitely be tension built up within oneself ending up producing unsatisfactory results. This indicates that academic performance is higher among students who used time-saving strategies, whereas those who did not use any time-saving measures for their school projects performed poorly in academics and even disliked the task because of disarray in managing things; therefore they postponed doing it until it is late.

One responsibility of a professor is to create an engaging learning atmosphere that meets all the safety requirements of the classroom. Students are encouraged to do right things and assist each other when instructors foster safe environment with set rules. In addition, extrinsic motivators can help students understand classroom expectations thus promoting intrinsic motivation. These types of motivators include praise, positive reinforcement, and rewards for good behavior. It just means that a student's place or environment really affects their learning and the performance they give whenever there are tasks and classes. This table also shows that students are aware of what one's own areas can bring to them whenever studying would take place in these particular sites. To sum up everything, as factors impacting on the productivity level as well as academic performance of respondents, learning environments have a composite mean score 3.14 interpreted as agree. This means that the productivity level definitely influenced by learning environment. Secondly having proper surroundings helps students concentrate on their task at hand so they will be able to perform better in class. Teachers need to bear in mind that it is essential for them to consider the materials they will use in teaching so that students can better study and be productive. Students will benefit more from a well-prepared environment.

Teacher job satisfaction is partly determined by the support of colleagues. Not only should students have the support of their peers but their teachers too. This makes everyone more positive and it has a lot of benefits to them in the end. It was researchers' opinion that no signal could mean anything other than agree. In other words, this means that even these student professors still depend on each other for support despite changes

in the way they teach and learn outside class buildings. The fact is that students as well as teachers can put to use any kind of aid they may require from themselves. It influences learners' academic performance positively sometimes. This illustrates how pupils do better in school when others help them out, though not always having said so indirectly by using different expressions for consent according to a study done by professors who work at universities (Wang & Nuru, 2017). Supporting each other provided good dealing with stress for faculty members. They felt more positivity about everything and any tasks they had to complete were not a problem anymore because of peer encouragement. That is why students were helped in continuing with what they had been assigned by their relatives or close people surrounding them during their studying process there. If this happens, then they will be able to concentrate on what they are doing now instead of getting distracted away from it. Students also develop social interaction skills and feel connections with those around them which contributes to mental health conditions favorable within a student. It reflects existence of a strong bond between them. By this it can be understood that online learning gives enough room for peer support among students. Accordingly, Srinivas & Venkatkrishnan (2016) confirmed such points mentioned like isolation from other students or teachers and professors as well as university staff. Peer contribution is an optional thing where online education could be transformed into something beneficial. It might act as an additional source of help apart from tutors or colleges. This form provided relief so that many of them felt more comfortable than before.

Teachers and parents should provide proper guidance in online learning to help learners understand and use wisely the educational, vocational, and personal opportunities they have or can develop. Proper guidance is a systematic assistance aimed at enabling learners adjust to school and life satisfactorily. All respondents answered agree as per the researchers' interpretation. This implies that most students who engage in online learning are well guided by their parents as well as professors. Learners play a great role in how performance activities are done and how they are assessed. Conceptual repetition, course requirements, and class work instructions among others are much obvious so that students may get completely acquainted with the subject matter. However, no one has reached at the higher explanation which is strongly agree. Therefore, this means that it is not well-directed by parents or lecturers but given because it helps students know how knowledge can be understood and quickly learn during remote studying sessions. According to Maryville University (2020) article families fear that isolation would become a problem for college students taking online courses. Thus, these learners might struggle with staying connected if they lack social connections. Additionally, emotional cues can be very difficult to interpret using video platforms online for students too. Not having any personal connection stifles advanced learners' social skills development.

The resources available within a family are essential in ensuring that students have a good life. A well-funded individual can effectively and efficiently undertake academic activities. Hence, the student will only concentrate on his or her studies complemented with some sort of extracurricular activities that would assist him/her to become a rounded person. The responsibility of sending children to school where it is their right over others rests upon parents as primary duty bearers. All respondents' answers were categorized

as agreement by researchers who interpreted them; this indicates that majority of the students are backed up by their families in terms of money and also moral support during this 'new normal' way of learning. This means that the guardian or parents are supporting the students in terms of financially and emotionally throughout their new normal education. In conclusion, there was a composite mean score of 3.12 for family resources as a factor influencing participants' productivity level and academic performance which was interpreted as agreement. This implies that because the parent is the one who offers financial aid to his child so he can finish school admitting thus being responsible both morally and financially for his welfare, they play an important role in determining how productive or inefficient any given student ends up being at school. Parental involvement is crucial to a child's success at school. Parent-engagement is when parents either orally or physically aid in their children's schooling. Mothers and fathers can also be present at home and/or at school – however they choose to remain attached to their children's lives – holding out great hope for those very young ones born yesterday. Biological Parents become involved primarily based on how they build up meanings for themselves as parents through participation in educational programs offered by schools for example; indeed such actions contribute towards better feelings about knowing how effective they are supposed to be concerning enhancing academic achievements among pupils while attending classes.

Based on table 25, the five factors which impacts students' level of productivity as well as academic performance are like for instance peer support. According to these results, peer support (3.17) is ranked first and indicated that it was agreed upon by verbal interpretation based on the composite mean. That means that the answer will be significantly be affective through their response to this question in relation to their level of productivity and academic achievement. It implies also that although student-teachers may have different methods of being instructed now, they still receive each other's assistance and know how to go about it even when they are not at school. This shows that both students and teachers can get assistance from it. Having a complete course plan given out to learners plus an agreement on working with others provides enough motivation required for moving forward in educating more about themselves during the process of performing a task or any other activity. As per Paris (2019), peer groups are thought to have a substantial impact on student. If the group atmosphere is warm, understanding, helpful then group influence or motivation, task performance and achievement will most probably be positive. Therefore having continuous support from those close to them makes them conclude tasks they set aside for themselves. This enables them to see sense in what they do thus keeping away their minds from being distracted thus maintaining focus on whatever they do. Positively such studies indicated that "support coming from classmates and even family" is significant in helping "a learner belongings meaning that getting help from others can make each learner more fruitful or informative" while "peer support coming from teachers classmates siblings" does promote the educational accomplishments of students over time." Supportive family members were parents who often gave help after classes by doing homework together or checking exercises; there were peers who provided moral backing; visiting friends in college who helped solve difficult questions; lecturers carried out extra tutorials during weekends since some topics proved to be tough.

Table 26 showed that time management had a significant relationship with all the perceived effects of new normal approach on education as factors influencing the students' academic performance and productivity. In another study conducted by Machebe, et. al (2017), most students agreed that success of online learning experience is impacted by effective time management. Fostering relationships through time management was positively related because teacher's monitoring ways to consider the student's presence in class are based on this relationship as well as how students organize their respective schedules. They noted that relationship can increase the academic performance of the learners (Dyer et al, 2018). Those moments when students value positive relations it happens in their lives when they have an opportunity to spend time with other people conversing freely for example. If they need it, then they could be able to integrate with the online classroom and increase ability and confident to seek out resources once. The findings also revealed that time management had significant relationship with engagement as perceived effects of new normal approach in education. These facts show how more students' engagement can be enhanced if teachers used certain tools or resources. Indeed, whenever possible all lessons, learning materials and activities were posted at LMS so far which boosts student engagement since they can fix their schedule straight away. This is consistent with Morgado (2015) who stated that managing one's time is crucial especially in final exams since it affects overall results and accomplishments of someone. Moreover, this suggested that there was a correlation between time management and students' engagement. Students should observe and prioritize their task and responsibilities once this principle is incorporated into future industry practice from this day on by making sure that all activities are completed before leaving school premises so as to heighten your level of interest through active involvement through the use of appropriate instructional strategies like group discussion sessions among others where one has obtained enough information about each topic addressed thus enabling you become more enlightened with business concepts while at school; having them engaged would mean meeting deadlines on all course requirements. On the other hand, time management had significant relationship with timeliness as perceived effects of new normal approach in education. Majority of students who prefer online classes have no need to trail behind regular classes at school. Accordingly, these students take their studies depending on the situation. They could also do their studies while doing other activities like running small business or family bonding among others. Many online classes are set-up with high adaptability (Sellers, 2016). Ample room for flexibility is allowed in this case where deadlines are incorporated into the course. The teachers can fix the schedules and the students need to set his own timetable to complete the coursework. Similarly, this suggested that it can cause challenges to students who have difficulty in keeping or following the timetable. Communication is one of those factors affecting academic performance; it had significant relationship with time management as perceived effects of new normal approach in education. Various studies had showed that academic performance is influenced by the communication skills of the students and teachers. All children's achievements depend on how well they understand instructions given. Online education has also been enhanced through teaching aids such as online materials (O'Doherty, 2018) and thus making communication within a culture meaningful during particular periods even when they may not be able to meet face-to-face because these forms of distance learning require continuing interaction based on specific

educational objectives agreed upon earlier between trainers and trainees before embarking on such academic pursuits aimed at satisfying their respective career goals within existing legal frameworks as stipulated under national legislation going forward into our future institutional socio-economic development plans for a greater society worldwide having more citizens being equipped academically than ever before through proper application various technological devices used today including smart phones connected internet networks access world wide web sites where both parties involved communicate each other without physical presence which allows exchanging information across geographical locations globally due globalization trend intensifying competition levels. This means that an online environment which is in good shape can bring together many different opportunities that involve both synchronous and asynchronous communication modes for students and teachers to share information as well as work together. The study further revealed that time management correlated with technology as perceived effects of new normal approach in education. The teaching and learning process is not limited to the classroom because of the help of technology. This rapid growth in technology has paid full price for the arrival and development of technology and its application to teaching. In reality, this ushered in technological advances that enabled learners to manage their time well. They can complete all the assignments within a given period. Mobile technology has become one of the central tools used during lessons; it is employed by teachers in shortest possible terms. This research also revealed that mobile devices such as smartphones are having so positive effect on improving education and learning (Ching-Wen, 2015). One way through which teachers could use mobile technology involves combining skills with applications that enhance certain aspects of learning. Moreover, teachers who were familiar with software programs before moving completely online have an advantage here. This implies well-utilized time in transition means being favored or placed at an advantageous position. As well, there is a significant relationship between time management and organization as perceived effects of new normal approach in education. Class scheduling was clearly outlined on how synchronous and asynchronous classes will be conducted online. Since schedules were already set up, organized online classes leads to good time management too. Kudari (2016) explained that if implemented consistently across different courses then study habits would have a bearing on academic performance hence influencing academic performance levels among college students hence doing them simultaneously would earn similar marks for all subjects.. If we want better results our studies should seriously consider this advice. Finally, relationships between time management and flexibility were also identified by the study. Online courses are flexible ones. Accordingly, Sanchez said they merge their course works together with research and learning tasks done at home allowing students choose when, where, how or what they want for studies in this situation. As he added, teachers can customize content and provision to the needs and background of their students. Not only do new ways of doing things need the new standard, but also new ways of thinking. This represents a shift to more imaginative, student-centered approaches pedagogies and practice. Meaning, the students have capability to create their timetable and schedules accommodating some lee ways for other personal matters or agenda.

Table 27 by the way showed a significant relationship between the learning environment and all of the perceived effects of new normal approach in education as factors influencing academic performance and productivity level of students. For instance,

Young (2019) says that if students view their learning environment positively and favorably, they can learn more effectively. Positive environments have students who belong, trust others, and are encouraged to take on challenges, try out new things, and ask questions. Since they are always with a student every time, he/she studies, people who come into contact and spend time with them belong to students' environment even outside school. Bates (2018) is consistent with this when she states that relationships refer to supportive learning environments where good interactions among learners such as children to adults in schools promote co-operations that breed trustfulness. This sense of connection to education is associated with greater attendance rates, higher grades, better scores on standardized tests, longer time spent in school. Furthermore, it was found out through a study that learnt environment had significant relation to engagement as perceived effect of new normal approach in education. Moreover, School in Rose Valley article mentioned engaged learning environments which improve children's concentration and awareness; contribute to high - quality learning experiences; develop pupils' higher-order critical thinking skills; result in enhanced overall student achievement levels. When there is a bond between one another plus the educator(s)", students tend towards collaborative active learning styles. Learning should involve feelings and emotions apart from rational thought based educational material or subject knowledge acquisition alone for it be motivating for learners at all times not just when supported by other conditions. It also allows for more customized learning experiences whereby each learner works at his own pace of development irrespective of what the others are doing or how fast they completed their assignments or projects if any were given at all. Similarly, there exists a significant relationship between timeliness and its perception as an effect from new normal approach on the condition concerning the educational system. Students reside in different learning environments than one another. They must adjust themselves based on their environment to be able to gainfully utilize their time. Certainly, even though it is now only a virtual school and the study areas differ for them, students should know how to enter and exit class on time. Time management that can start from there is a very good practice which they also have at their disposal until they are employed somewhere else in future. On the other hand, communication has significant influence on learning environment as factors affecting academic performance as this describes perceived effects of new normal approach in education. Evidently, good learning environment requires effective communication between professors and learners within a particular institution or course of study. This was proper way of engaging with others whom they were studying with alongside among others like discussing about school issues amidst all the rest items being covered together by students in particular on papers presented by lecturers or students themselves as well. Communication processes must be open so that information can flow freely from lecturers to students or among the learners themselves hence onwards mooting student-teacher relations let alone teacher-student communications. Likewise, ETRP Moodle Site article confirms that communication channels are crucial especially for an ideal learning atmosphere subjected into thorough analysis and these include but not limited to what others might assume about them at first sight such as one – way exchange of information versus interactive discourse meant for expanding own understanding plus providing support during conventional instruction periods. The provision of logistical information as well as social context contributes towards healthier supportive learning environments too. Incorporation of technology in

the learning environment is considered as one of the effects of the “new normal” approach. Right now, this is happening for all students across the globe during this pandemic period. So, everyone currently uses technology to keep on studying at school via their mobile phones or laptops to access online lessons. As per Spector, et.al. (2018), a modern-day learning environment naturally blends tech into flexible teaching areas for better student engagement and integration with solo-small class-whole class that is believed to be important for student success today. Additionally, organization had significant relationship with learning environment as perceived impact of new normal approach in education. For them to concentrate and enjoy learning, the place where they study should be well arranged. Effective learning environments are also those that are literate and meaningful, accessible and organized, but most importantly realistic. Teaching and learning is hard in an untidy disorganized unfriendly condition between learners and educators. A large portion of their time is consumed by students in their learning environment; hence it needs to be exciting and inviting for anyone who wants to learn anything more about it. Hence what they value, believe about teaching-learning process and students’ knowledge are depicted in a given place of studying. Lastly, findings from this study also demonstrated that there were significances relationships between learning environment as well as flexibility. Since students’ ability to move around freely while studying depends on whether their classrooms have enough space or not just ergo will be analyzed alone below however these are not only several ways through which teachers can impart knowledge on other subjects into minds like long jump among others because professors may opt for other approaches too through which they can teach them things discussed above which happens in most classrooms as you will see later on in this report so stay tuned though it does vary slightly from professor-to-professor”. Whenever pupils think about a flexible schooling room, they think solely about the physical space. It is a fact that while the nature of space allows it to be adaptable, flexible learning environment goes beyond this aspect to take into account various other factors like the arrangement of furniture in class. Other aspects of the learning environment addressed in modern, flexible learning environments include how students are grouped during learning and how time can be used more freely throughout the day.

The analysis in Table 28 showed that peer support had a strong correlation with all the perceived effects of the new normal approach in education as academic performance factors and student productivity. The peer support was strongly related to fostering relationship as a new normal effect in education. In this time of pandemic, there is a great chance that students are studying alone, maybe somewhere in their rooms so that they can avoid being distracted or disturbed by other people hence losing focus. But this will affect a student’s life for sure. It should however promote relationship with others so that the student feels he/she is not alone and someone from his/her peers can stand with him/her. Relationship according to Inclusive Education creates a sense of belonging which is vital for learning. Create an environment where students help one another and learn together. Many teenagers find school to be lonely because having classmates who do not accept them well has been linked to disengagement from class work and low grade earning among learners. Additionally, the study found out that engagement had significant association with peer support as perceived effect of new normal approach in education. Though students might feel far from others due to today’s learning format, gaining support through their fellow students really helps them keep engaged in learning thus positively

impacting on their academic lives at large. This is supported by Hakimzadeh (2016) research whose findings indicated substantial positive relationships between measures of perceived peer support, academic engagement and satisfaction with life among dyads/roommates. Both positive impacts were realized when it comes to peer support on learner participation in school activities as well as achieving contentment later on life after schooling. Moreover, timeliness had also significant relationship within peer support as factors affecting the academic performance under this kind of perception about teaching methods as hinted by the study. There is a need for us to know what our students are doing in order to establish if they are timely or not through checking them out personally. Informed about their weekly schedule even having set deadlines helps the students manage their time for tasks and activities that need to be done. Also, the study found out that communication had significant relationship on peer support as factors affecting the academic performance as perceived effects of new normal approach in education as indicated by research results. Especially that students really need peer support especially in this time of pandemic. Since all students are not close to classmates anymore and cannot have any physically contact with them, but they still can communicate through social media platforms. This is so important in providing supportive communications since it will help further understanding of a particular situation. Peer Supporter should have excellent communication skills, be an active listener and problem solver while addressing a peer's issue either formally or informally (Sarah, 2015). Also, the new normal approach in education as perceived effects of technology have a significant relationship with peer support as factors affecting the academic performance. . This is one of the best ways to maintain support for students, who can be communicated through it. Also, organization perceived effects of new normal approach in education had significant relationship with peer support as factors affecting the academic performance. An article from Stanford University that spoke to anybody and engaged in places they could learn a lot by mingling among themselves. They improve their capacity to organize learning events, cooperate with others, provide/receive feedback, and self- evaluate their own learning. Lastly, peer support as factors affecting the academic performance had also significant relationship on flexibility as perceived effects of new normal approach in education. It is common for instructors who want to use LMSs to develop curriculum that can be shared and distributed among students while monitoring their progress at the same time. Some features of a Learning Management System include threaded conversations, video conferencing, discussion forums etc. It states that higher education LMSs are used for digital instruction. This means that learners can now study at home without having to travel long distances. Likewise, teachers may keep giving lectures and teaching young people how things work. What it does provide them is the ability to remain normal despite all odds because this offers them an opportunity to maintain some kind of stability within their everyday lives

Table 29 showed that Proper Guidance was a factor, which affected students' academic performance and productivity levels. Furthermore, it indicated that there was a significant relationship with all the perceived effects of new normal approach in education. As they progress in their studies, students' desire increased autonomy as well as intellectual independence. It is possible to use online learning for personal study programs such as those comprising college-level courses. When complemented by practical exercises, real experiences and strict evaluation measures they enable faster

acquisition of knowledge by them. In exploring other areas, students may wish to try out some introductory topics before deciding on which path to follow. Thus, fostering relationships would be significant because children's emotional handling is based on what they are told and taught about themselves by teachers or parents speaking from experience. Ideally, having someone who properly guides them through words of wisdom or encouragement during new normal approach in education could lead into high productivity level and an outstanding academic performance (Diemer and Voight, 2022). Similarly proper guidance had a significant relationship with engagement among others perceived effects of new normal approach in education (Klem and Connell, 2021). This indicates that teachers who interact with students when guiding them assist them complete assignments done online or at home including corresponding activities. Our concern went beyond the learning activity to understand how talk prompts the teacher to engage students along constructive modes of participation, active and passive modes of involvement adopted by learners and thus categories stem from these modes that facilitate transfer (Graham et al., 2008). According to Chi et al. (2018), "Interactive," "Constructive," "Active" and "Passive" teaching methods were introduced throughout different course units to analyze how effectively teachers applied these principles in creating appropriate learning activities and worksheets". However, little has been done regarding how teachers solicit different forms of student engagement with their talk, which is perhaps the most common form of teacher guidance. Moreover, proper guidance had a significant relationship with time among others perceived effects of new normal approach in education (Klem and Connell, 2021). The teachers explain to students how to utilize time resources through words like objectives, instructions, format and grading rubric in each activity they post. This enables students to manage their time well and avoid wasting it. For instance, the abilities of students in managing their own times could be a function not only of what they do but also on how they think about time. Sense of urgency of the students is connected on the proper guidance performed by the teachers. Students who care less feel that they are focused on one task and ignore the need to keep track of time. They put all their efforts into an assignment when they realize it has to be done. Once pupils believe that they have some understanding about what they are doing, then higher grades can be recorded by them for themselves."

The other factor that affects the level of productivity and academic achievement for these students is the availability of family resources which assist in communication and education. They should increase opportunities for online learning as they may be less costly compared to traditional classrooms. It could also mean that students have to skip certain things so as to meet their needs. To begin with, due to having resources, this enables them think peacefully such that they can complete their programs. Moreover, if students are aware that their parents are well-off, it becomes easier for them to concentrate on their studies. Table 30 indicates that family resources like materials and technology were associated with all the perceived effects of new normal approach in education significantly influencing performance levels. When parents have enough money; therefore, providing psychological support by supervising and guiding kids' reading activities at home signifies more success at school than any other contrary situation they find themselves in thus being a positive outcome of social change taking place across generations. Some people say who is more involved in student's training or educating then what level the family income does play major role towards determining

his/her success. New normal relatedness could not omit the families' resourcefulness' influence on educational fostering relationships score. The ability of students to create a harmonious relationship with teachers and peers has been highlighted by this research. As Cerna and Pavliushchenko (2015) argue using Maslow's theory someone may reach fostering relationship (belongingness need) upon fulfilling basic necessities (basic resources). Correspondingly, having parent – student relationship would enable one know exactly where his/her family stands in terms of finance. Most parents do teach their children how they will manage their finances while still studying at college; hence making most young adults leave home during college: it is necessary for students' guardians/parents to guide these young ones since most likely they are in the hospitality industry when working from far away from home and being independent. Also, students who have close attention caring about the family resources from their parents can form good relationships. For example, they may learn how to save money or budget simply by observing how their parents talk about these topics and make financial decisions, which is a type of financial socialization. However, some of their habits might affect their children unintentionally. If for instance a student feels uneasy discussing income or debt with them for whatever reason, they will have to get any clues that are available.

No significant differences are evident in the perceived effects of new normal approach in education among respondents who were classified by sex. Therefore, students considered the "new normal" similarly whether they were males or females. Table 32 provided no significant differences in the perceived impacts of new normal approach in education when the respondents are confined to different year grades. This means no matter what grade level you are as a student, you share similar perceptions towards new ways of teaching and learning at school. The research outlines that equality is practiced at all income levels and online payment systems, assignments, discussions, etc., which are based on expertise of teachers themselves. It was suggested by Cerna (2015) that today's schools should have more academic and psychological support for their students. That will be crucial when increasing numbers of students struggle to adapt to these changes in teaching methods. While it may take some time and effort to adjust traditional assessment approaches to these new paradigms, doing so will help ensure learning quality and the validity of final exams. There was no difference between rare types of learners such as irregular or regular students because both can receive equal treatment as well as lessons. However, this finding demonstrates that distance learning is helpful regardless your status/position as far as being a student is concerned. The table 34 did not show any considerable variance on how differently various locations influenced educational perception on 'new normal' conceptuality. It just shows where students come from with nothing much attached to it. They agree about it equally among them all, it supports these claims as its findings provide empirical evidence supporting the idea that the development of information communication technologies (ICTs) has effectively bridged gaps between learners and training programs despite potential barriers related to distance education provision. According to this research piece by Miller (2018), cell phones become learning tools especially when those taking pictures during interviews use them as notes or videos. Among other things, these include connectivity, mobility, interactivity and creativity that make smartphones great learning tools. Thus, mobile devices have the potential to change education if a new approach to connected training is introduced. In this system, there are innumerable ways for teachers and students to

personalize their learning, upgrade their education, consult professionals or use informational resources.

Conclusions

As the study findings indicated, the following deductions were made:

1. From this, results of the research reflects the perception of high dominance students in 2nd year level, regular and residence in Laguna. The study was participated by almost equal number of male and female students, however dominated by 2nd year level due to their highest population and majority is regular students and are residence of Laguna conducted virtual class.
2. On effects of new normal approach in education conducting blended learning among schools was conducted which were rated above average from a score scale despite being first time to fully online classes. The faculty members managed to take classes beyond what they expected. The students considered communication and flexibility as the best things about new normal approach in education. For instance platform like Learning Management System individual account of Office 365 existence social media applications that gets more way for class discussion through synchronous and asynchronous schedule sessions have been aimed at bringing all learners together with standard numbers assessment measures used for seeing good sides on this recent change done by school.
3. Many aspects influence student productivity level and academic performance among them being addressed by all students' concerns and questions leads to better understanding hence high quality work production will be observed within a short span of time. Peer support as well as learning environment are two important factors affecting student's productivity level as well as academic performance therefore should be improved if we want our student's performance be excellent always. Because I never knew any place or group who could manage themselves without brotherhood love or sense but left alone needing assistance from other shoulders besides peers support is always vital for all not only some people or places.
4. Having good fostering relationship, right engagement, timeliness, communication, usage of technology in an organization is a way through which he/she can receive high grades whenever one is undertaking his/her studies under such situations caused by COVID-19 pandemic. Nothing is impossible but all these seem very difficult when it comes to leaving their comfort zones. The conduct of blended learnings of school produced an excellent point of view

- for pupil to see the positive side of it and convert to outstanding academic routine.
5. Demographical status has no impact on the ability of a student from being taught and adapting to the new normal approach in education. New normal approach was delivered by schools in the broadest and most equal way possible among students. To this end, all that is necessary is ensuring fair delivery of lessons and accomplishment method.
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Recommendations

Recommendations by the researchers based on the study's findings are as follows:

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1. The study can be replicated using a psychographic profile of the respondents and qualitative fibre optics for all student populations from first up to fourth level in Laguna.
 2. Recommendations are given towards students' adherence to time management and due-date compliance orientation. The students need to understand how they spend their time, therefore, adhering strictly to a timetable is important.
 3. The parents and faculty members must allocate more time and attention to guiding students into an appropriate professional path. Besides performance outcome for students, parents may also provide teaching aids and electronic gadgets. Professors should have perspectives or opinions; restate concepts and provide additional explanations until students stay in focus with them. These will help learners have an opportunity to seek something higher in education besides maintaining productivity gains throughout the year and being able to achieve high performance targets.
 4. To ensure good academic performance among them, there must be a positive perceived effect on students. Therefore, schools should monitor each student's performance. The schools could also organize webinars that can guide teachers on how they can make correct perceptions that appeal to kids as well as maintain those thus preventing learners from forgetting about the new normal of learning. In order for this to happen, there is great help when someone knows each student in relation to managing the positive perceived effect which leads good academic performance of pupils.
 5. The school should continue using standards implemented during blended learnings including having equal numbers of assessment measures for different courses per semester agreed sessions of synchronous and asynchronous session use of LMS & Office 365 , so that every student can follow what were done every

day even if they are far away from his or her place like locations aside mobile device type

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research adhered strictly to ethical principles, ensuring comprehensive compliance with all necessary protocols. Prior approvals were secured, and informed consent was obtained from all participants, who were also informed of their freedom to withdraw from the study at any time. Anonymity was maintained through the use of pseudonyms, and data was securely stored to safeguard the respondents' well-being.

Proper citations were employed to prevent plagiarism, and objectivity was upheld through formal communication and an unbiased interpretation of the findings. Additionally, no conflict of interest existed in the conduct of the study. Comprehensive data, files, and documentation were meticulously compiled to support the research, and the results were used purely for research purposes.

Trust with participants was fostered, their anonymity was protected, and potential biases were identified and mitigated. The ethical framework was further reinforced by rigorous validation strategies, including triangulation and member checking.

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